

Detection and Visualization of Anarchic Constructions Based on 3D City Modeling: A Case Study Kelibia City Tunisia

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Résumé: Cet article présente une méthodologie de détection et de visualisation des bâtiments anarchiques basée sur la modélisation des villes en 3D. Cette méthodologie comprend quatre parties : la détection des changements, la détection des bâtiments anarchiques, la modélisation 3D de la ville et la visualisation des changements et des bâtiments anarchiques détectés. Cette modélisation 3D est définie comme un niveau de détail (LoD1) du modèle de ville 3D généré à partir des empreintes de bâtiment ainsi de plusieurs données hétérogènes dérivées de plusieurs sources. Par conséquent, cet article met en évidence plusieurs défis liés à la détection des changements de construction et présente un état de l'art des techniques et des méthodes de détection des changements à partir des données hétérogènes issues de plusieurs sources de données. Cet article présente également une revue d'un certain nombre d'approches et de techniques actuelles de modélisation de villes en 3D afin d'élaborer un aperçu des défis liés à l'extraction de villes en 3D.

Mots-clés : Modélisation des villes en 3D, modèle 3D de ville, détection de changement 3D, détection de changement des bâtiments, empreintes de bâtiments, détection des bâtiments anarchiques, CityGML

Abstract This paper presents a methodology of detection and visualization of anarchic buildings

based on 3D City Modeling. This methodology includes four parts, change detection, anarchic building detection, 3D City Modeling and visualization of change and anarchic building detected. This 3D City Modeling is defined as a level of detail (LoD1) of 3D city model that is generated from building footprint using several data derived from multiple sources. Hence, this paper highlights several challenges of building change detection, and presents a state of art of techniques and methods of change detection from several data types. The current paper will review also a number of current approaches and techniques of 3D city modeling in order to elaborate an overview of challenges related to of 3D city extraction.

Keywords: 3D City modeling, 3D city model, 3D change detection, Building change detection, building footprint, anarchic building detection, CityGML

I. Introduction

During the last few years, particularly those following the revolution in Tunisia, the urban plan has known in several cities an anarchic human influence and an extension without development. Anarchic building construction can be a problematic issue on densely populated cities, especially because it leads to unbalanced urban structure. The urban development plan define a maximum boundary for building coverage and floor ratios, but practically it is challenging to apply the plans to the real life in partly unplanned cities that are going under urban transformation, such as « kelibia » in Tunisia. Many new buildings need to be constructed every year. Obviously, constructing a new building requires the municipality permission. However, unfortunately some of the constructors do not get building permission, which ends in an anarchic expansion of buildings. Therefore, existence of an efficient method of anarchic building monitoring is necessary to reduce the costs, time and man power. This method should be automatic and quick. Accurate, precise and up to date spatially referenced information is required for proper management and planning in anarchic buildings monitoring and undertaking precautionary measures required. In this research, the aim is to present a methodology of anarchic Buildings detection based on 3D City Modeling that is fast enough and cost effective.

This paper is organized as follows: The following section reviews many techniques and methods of building change detection from several data types. Section 3 presents the study area and a description of our data. In Section 4 the methodology of this research is presented. We present in section 5 the 3D city model of Kelibia, it provides also a number of current approaches and techniques of 3D city modeling. Finally, conclusions and future work are provided in section 6.

II. State of the art

Acquiring multi-temporal satellite images and using image-processing techniques for automatic change detection is one of the useful methods, which can be used in Illegal Buildings monitoring [3]. On one hand, automatic anarchic Buildings monitoring causes significant cost reduction compared to that of currently used methods and on the other hand, it reduces manpower and consequently, the collusion between municipal inspectors and constructors. Extensive researches have been undertaken in the area of building detection. However, a few studies have been reported in the field of anarchic Buildings detection. The main deference of the mentioned studies is the method of building change detection. Ahmad [1] detected the changes in high density urban and rural areas using

multi-temporal high resolution IKONOS satellite images. He made the images orthorectified in order to make the image measurements consistent with the ground measurements. Benedek et al. [4] introduced a probabilistic approach of building extraction in remotely sensed images. They also constructed a flexible hierarchical framework, which can create various building appearance models from different elementary feature-based modules. Singhal and Radhika [21] proposed a method for detecting the buildings from high-resolution color aerial images using color invariance property and canny edge detection technique. Xu et al. [25] proposed an approach to automatically detect and classify changes in buildings from two epochs of airborne laser scanner data, which verifies the changes by making rules on the difference image map. Then, they classify changes belonging to buildings in the difference image map to detect Illegal Buildings. Hermosilla et al. [11] compared and evaluated two main approaches including threshold-based and object-based classification for automatic building detection and localization using high spatial resolution imagery and LIDAR data. Chen et al. [6] proposed a building change detection framework based on 3D reconstruction. This framework uses the UAV aerial images to reconstruct the 3D geometry of a region, which is lightweight and simple operate for quick change detection compared to expensive 3D geometry model based approaches. Zhou et al. [26] proposed a novel approach to derive 3D geometric building changes by comparing new VHR images (taken at time T1) to existing LiDAR data (obtained at time T0). Jovanović et al. [12] proposed a method based on comparison of object-based and pixel-based image analysis approaches to automatically detect newly built, changed or demolished buildings using VHR images. D. Santos et al. [19] proposed a method for building change detection using LiDAR data, the main contribution of this method is related to the use of height entropy concept to classify the change areas into building or vegetation. It was robust in detecting building changes, having also the potential to identify small changes (larger than 20 m²). Chaabane et al. [8] proposed an approach based on expert knowledge that Detection and Visualization of Anarchic Constructions Based on 3D City Modeling allows identifying illegal buildings by using a specified ontology intended for combining semantic rules translated to concepts (Table 1)

Table 1: State of the art, techniques and methods of building change detection

Authors	DATA	Methods / Techniques	Application
Jovanović et al. (2021) [12]	*VHR images	Comparison of object-based and pixel-based image analysis approaches	Building Change Detection
Karuppusamy (2021) [13]	*3D and 2D data	Convolutional neural networks (CNN)	Building Detection
D. Santos et al. (2020) [19]	*3D information from multi-temporal LIDAR Scanning	Height entropy concept (classification of the change areas into building)	Automatic Building Detection
Chaabane et al. (2019) [8]	*VHR images * Expert knowledge	Classification approach : combining classified VHR images and formalized semantic rules	Anarchic Urban Expansions Detection and Monitoring
Namouchi et al.(2022) [17]	* LIDAR data * Multi-spectral images	Automatic segmentation approach	Boundaries extraction and 3D urban modeling
Varol et al. (2019) [5]	*LIDAR data *Development plans	Comparing LIDAR data and stereo KOMPSAT-3 images with development plans	Illegal Constructions Detection
Zhou et al. (2018) [26]	*LiDAR data *VHR images	Comparing new VHR images to existing LiDAR data	3D Building Change Detection
Chen et al. (2015) [6]	*Aerial images	Building change detection Framework based on 3D reconstruction	Building Change Detection
Moghadam et al. (2015) [16]	*Multi-temporal satellite images *Geospatial Information System (GIS)	K-means clustering technique	Automatic Illegal Buildings Detection
Zhu et al. (2015) [27]	*Oblique airborne images	Feature line based method	Building Detection and Reconstruction
Singhal and Radhika (2014) [21]	*High resolution color aerial images	Color invariance property and canny edge detection technique	Building Detection
Xu et al. (2013) [25]	*Airborne laser scanner data	Classification approach (making rules on the difference image map)	Automatic Illegal Buildings Detection
Hermosilla et al. (2011) [11]	*high spatial resolution images and LIDAR data	Approaches including threshold-based and object-based classification	Automatic Building Detection
Benedek et al. (2010) [4]	* Remote Sensing Images	Probabilistic approach	Building Extraction
Bayburt et al. (2008) [3]	*Multi-temporal satellite images	Image processing techniques	Automatic Building Change Detection
Ahmad (2005) [1]	*Multi-temporal satellite images	Images orthorectified	Change Detection in high density urban

III. Study area and data

1. Case Study

The study area of this research is a part of the north-eastern of Tunisia which covers 1100 hectares located between $36^{\circ} 51' N$ and $11^{\circ} 05' E$, The KELIBIA region. This area is chosen because it presents a problematic city with complicated building structures, illegal floor construction, and anarchic urban expansions around rivers, agricultural regions and along the sea. All these factors make this area one of the best challenging candidate for this study.

2. Data description

The available data for this area (Kelibia city) are: an Ortho-image (1) was acquired in 2016 (Photogrammetry, 0.1*0.1m) ; the Urban Development Plans (2), the digital terrain model (3) DTM (Raster, Photogrammetry, 1*1m), the digital surface model DSM (4) (Raster, Photogrammetry, 1*1m), the maritime public domain (5) (MPD), the hydraulic public domain (6) (HPD). These data have been collected and generated with a strong help and assistance from urban experts.

Figure 1: (1) Ortho-image (2) Urban Development Plans (5) MPD (6) HPD

IV. Methodology

The proposed methodology can be divided into four parts, which include change detection, Anarchic building (AB) detection, 3D city modeling (generated from buildings footprint) and visualization of change and Anarchic building detected as highlighted in the flowchart shown in Figure 2. The input data are building footprint data, DTM, DSM and the Urban Development Plans, whereas the output corresponds to buildings change information in VR system. The footprints are cartographic GIS data in ArcGIS Shapefile format, providing the two-dimensional extent of buildings. The study area includes 2423 building footprints representing a variety of building types. The Footprint data have been integrated with difference of surface elevation data (*dDSM*), to construct 3D building models.

Figure 2 : The flowchart of methodology
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1. Change Detection

We start with the process of change detection using the difference height threshold. A Digital Surface Model (DSM) is a simple and compatible 3D format for top-view change detection. Finding 2 out the differences of the registered 3D data. DSM is a mathematical surface which includes vegetation, buildings, and the other visible objects on the ground $dDSM$. This latter is a model, which is obtained using result from the removal of Digital Terrain Model (DTM) of DSM, and includes the object heights, like vegetation, trees and buildings.

$$dDSM = DSM - DTM \quad (1)$$

The difference DSM $dDSM$ is obtained employing Equation 1. It corresponds to a height difference map, which allows locating the potential change areas. Similarly, a height threshold (TH) is employed to eliminate the small height variations [22]. If the pixels with absolute values larger than the height the threshold are labeled as potential changes, otherwise, they are considered as no changes. From the city planning rules and municipality database we aim to identify and represent the type of change. In general, the information of change can be represented in 3 categories (Table 2). In this research we represent change according to 3 types: legal change, illegal change and area under constructions.

Table 2: Change representation

	Change representation	References
Type change	It requires a full change matrix that specifies the change direction of the land-cover.	Lu et al. [14]
Binary change	It provides a binary indicator on changed area / not-changed area.	Radke et al. [20]
Triple change mask	A triple indicator labels the status of the change: <u>Positive</u> (refers to increased height / reduced depth) <u>Negative</u> (refers to the opposite) and <u>Not-changed</u> .	Tian et al. [23]

2. Anarchic building detection

This part of our methodology includes anarchic buildings detection that is divided in two levels. We started by overlaying building footprint data with Urban Development Plans (UDP) which represents the information related to each zone of the urban plan such as urban zones, industrial zone, agricultural zone, commercial zone and forest zone. With this method we managed to extract the position of anarchic buildings, for example if according to the UDP an area is not an urban area, it is a green area, but the result of overlaying provided information that it is an urban area according to building footprint data. The second level is overlaying building footprint data with maritime public domain (MPD) and hydraulic public domain (HPD).

Figure 3: 2D Anarchic Constructions

Figure 4: (a) 3D Anarchic constructions vs (b) Anarchic constructions (Ground truth)

The obtained result by overlaying building footprint data with maritime public domain demonstrates that there are anarchic constructions on the shores of the sea. The DPM and the regulatory document define this anarchic construction as forbidden “No one can, without having permission for living there, occupying a dependency of the public domain...” Figure.3 illustrated anarchic constructions (visualization 2D in ArcGIS). And Figure.4.a and 4.b illustrated 3D anarchic constructions projected with ground truth (Ortho-image was acquired in 2016).

V. 3D City Modeling

1. Techniques and methods of 3D City

Modeling 3D city model is a digital representation of the Earth’s surface. It related objects such as building, vegetation, and some manmade feature belonging to urban area. It is a very useful for various applications such as for planning in Navigation, Disasters

Management, Transportations and Urban Environmental Managements. However, the applications of 3D city model in urban planning in Tunisia are not extended and the in-depth utility is not yet developed widely. So the Construction of 3D city models is a most interesting research topic in recent years. There are various terms used for 3D city models such as “Cyber town”, “Virtual City”, or “Digital City”. 3D city models are basically a computerized or digital model of a city contains the graphic representation of buildings and other objects in 2.5 or 3D. As illustrated in Figure 4, three main geomatic approaches are defined to 3D City modeling.

Figure 5: Geomatic approaches for 3D City Modeling

We present geomatic techniques for 3D City modeling. These techniques divided in to three main categories as detailed in Figure 5. The first category of methods is based on Automation (Automatic, Semi-automatic and Manual methods). The second is based on Data input techniques (Photogrammetry, Laser Techniques) and finally hybrid methods. We give an overview about the related Techniques with creation of 3D City models using geomatic Techniques. Photogrammetry, Laser grammetry, GPS, or combination of these geomatic techniques plays a major role to create a 3D City model. Kobayashi [13] proposes a relation between Photogrammetry and 3D City modeling. He suggests a technique for building 3D city models and he proposes a method for employing photogrammetric processing to create 3D city models. Also, he used aerial images to create a 3D city model using photogrammetry techniques, and he discusses the effectiveness of the 3D model in terms of time and reusability. Amat et al. [2] proposed a methodology to create 3D City model by using the combination of Aerial Photogrammetry and Close range Photogrammetry. Döllner et al. [7] created a 3D Berlin model .They developed a system for integrating, managing, presenting, and distributing complex urban geo-information. 3D city models, therefore, constitute a major concept in 3D geo information systems (3D GIS). In this projects Digital Aerials Photos, DTM, Geo-referenced thematic data, 3D data, Digital Architecture models, and Cadastral data used as input and 3D Geo-database System and 3D City model comes as output. Hanbali et al. makes a 3D model for Yarmouk University by using GIS and Photogrammetry techniques. Chen [6] created a 3D city mode by using 3D GIS City modeling and 3D modeling software. He aims to describe the integration of geo-informatics Detection and Visualization of Anarchic Constructions Based on 3D City Modeling

techniques with 3D modeling software to develop 3D GIS database which includes reconstruction of buildings.

Tsai et al. [24] developed a method for Texture Generation and Mapping by using Video Sequences for 3D Building Models. Ming et al. [15] proposed an approach that is useful to create the accurate and geo-referenced 3D photo-realistic models from point clouds and digital imagery. Over et al. [18] generated an interactive 3D City Models based on free geo-data available from the Open Street Map (OSM).

Figure 6: Five Levels-of-Detail (LoD) provided by CityGML

Those techniques for 3D City modeling are old. In recent years, creating 3D city model and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are increasingly popular. So building a 3D city model of an urban environment, deserve several data derived from multiple sources.

These sources include high resolution satellite imagery, LIDAR data and stereo aerial images. The multiple sources contain a large number of objects of different classes, structures and different data models. Hence, researchers face the problem of data; the biggest obstacle to fully exploit this data is variety, complexity and the heterogeneity of the source data formats. In this regard, City Geography Markup Language (CityGML) focuses on these problems [10]. CityGML is one of the first 3D standards and tools for displaying 3D geospatial data sets that allow representing together geometries and attributes and facilitating the 3D building data sharing. Moreover, the CityGML model offers the possibility to exchange and save easily the 3D dataset, since it has been developed as open standard model based on the xml format as described in Fissore and Pirotti (2019).

Figure 7: Five Levels-of-Detail (LoD) provided by CityGML

CityGML represents the geometrical, semantic, and visual aspects of 3D city models. The principal focus is on the semantic definitions of all objects that are relevant for applications of 3D city models: buildings and their parts, transportation objects, water bodies, vegetation, terrain, and furniture. It is the international standard of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) for the representation and exchange of 3D city models. The CityGML dataset contain and define information in five levels of detail starting from level 0 (LoD0) to level 4 (LoD4) as shown in the illustration in Figure 7.

The LoD4 presents interior structures like rooms, doors, stairs, and furniture. This representation presents our contribution to obtain 3D spatial data and minimizing the cost when used with its detailed levels. Therefore, to facilitate the 3D building data sharing we used a CityGML standard as the follows [5]: CityGML language for the 3D building models which are used with the Level of detail, ESRI Shapefile format for the 2D GIS data which includes 2D parcel and building contours and building height information, ESRI Shapefile format for the data that includes the geometric relations between building contours and 3D-Studio MAX and VRML file format for 3D building models.

2. 3D City Modeling of Kelibia

The Kelibia city 3D model utilises photogrammetry data that covers an area of 1100 km². The data collection system is an integrated one (digital camera, GPS, direct sensor navigation devices etc.). Geo-referenced LAS data, digital surface model (DSM), digital terrain model (DTM), difference digital surface model (dDSM), ortho-image and footprint buildings, 3D city model was created as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 8: 3D city model of kelibia, Tunisia

Various automatic corrections were made until the 3D city model was obtained with the desired details. In this work, to create our 3D city model of Kelibia, we first used the Digital terrain model (DTM), the buildings footprint and information related to their height obtained from combined dDSM (employing Equation 1.) and information from the Urban Development Plans (UDP); to represent our city to the level of detail LoD1. The Footprint data have been integrated with difference of surface elevation data (dDSM), to construct 3D building models. We used too other information related to buildings like the type of buildings; the floors number, the roof type, to enrich semantics of our 3D model. From all this information, the CityGML standard allowed us to automatically create LoD1 of kelibia city as shown in Figure. 7.

Conclusion

There are many useful applications of 3D city model in urban planning analysis, disaster management, tourism, telecommunication and other fields now. However, the applications of 3D city model in urban planning in TUNISIA are not extended and are not yet developed. This paper proposes a methodology for anarchic building detection based on 3D City Modeling; a case study of a part of the north-eastern of TUNISIA: Kelibia city. The main contribution is related to the 3D modeling using building footprint data.

Future work will take further steps into 3D modeling, visualization of 3D model of Kelibia city in Virtual Reality System (VRS), and interaction with change and anarchic building detected.

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